

Training & capacity building resources

Cos4Cloud Services

About the Authenix system and user guide

This is a system and user guide to [AUTHENIX](#), an online authentication service that provides access to multiple protected citizen science platforms and services via a Single-Sign-On and facilitates General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance for apps and services.

Description

This is a system guide to **AUTHENIX**, an online authentication service that facilitates data protection compliance for registered applications and websites. It provides users (i.e. citizen scientists and researchers) with the ability to access multiple citizen science platforms and services using a Single-Sign-On.

AUTHENIX has been developed by [Secure Dimensions](#) as part of [Cos4Cloud](#) a European Horizon 2020 funded project. The Cos4Cloud project has developed [thirteen services](#) boosting citizen science technological services to help increase and improve the quantity and quality of observations.

AUTHENIX facilitates General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) compliance for applications and websites registered, facilitating users with the option to use a Single-Sign-On a useful feature for citizen science platforms and services.

Service Coordinator

Cos4Cloud Coordinator

The following content has been provided to help guide users of this service.

WHAT IS AUTHENIX?

AUTHENIX is a user authentication service provider that targets citizen science platforms and services, as well as the data created, enhancing accessibility and possibilities for review and research. Once an entity is registered a login process that provides unique user IDs is supported.

WHO IS THIS SERVICE FOR AND WHAT ARE THE BENEFITS?

AUTHENIX provides a login service which brings together organisations, including universities, and particularly those who operate citizen science projects and services, facilitating registration of applications and websites providing GDPR compliance support. In doing so it can give users (i.e. citizen scientists and researchers) the ability to log in using third-party accounts (i.e. Facebook, Google etc.).

Through these integrated OAuth protocols and OpenID authentication, multiple citizen science platforms and services, for example, can be accessed using a Single-Sign-On system reducing the repetition of re-logins. **AUTHENIX** also connects to an Identity Federation called eduGAIN that facilitates Universities user login.

AUTHENIX has the potential to support citizen science and improve capabilities for research by reducing the impact of data silos, helping to make citizen science data more accessible, while providing opportunities to improve FAIR aspects based on GDPR compliant processing of personal data.

HOW DOES IT WORK?

As a user authentication service provider **AUTHENIX** acts as a broker of user authentication and personal information between Identity Providers and the Operators of registered applications. Identity Providers (IdP) facilitate the authentication and provides the personal information of the user. Through the registration process operators select the information they would like to request from users. This can include none, one or more of the following:

- IdP: identifies which third-party platforms used to log in (i.e. Facebook, Google, University, etc.)
- ID: creates a unique identifier for users
- Profile: collects personal information from users (name, surname, etc.)
- Email: collects the user's email address

Each IdP gains user consent to release personal information which enables user registration via the **AUTHENIX** service. If no options are selected, the user acts de-facto anonymously. Some options i.e *Profile* or *Email* require the operator to provide a privacy statement informing users about the personal data to be collected, why and how it will be used.

Once **AUTHENIX** is integrated an OpenID Connect token is provided for each app, website or service which includes the type of personal information requested which is based on the categories selected by the operator in registration. Each access token has a validity period which sets limits on the timeframe within which it can be used to fetch the pre-selected categories of personal data. Through this process there is no need to store personal information, which supports compliance to GDPR requirements.

HOW TO USE AUTHENIX – A STEP BY STEP GUIDE

Go through the steps below to understand how **AUTHENIX** can be integrated as part of the log in process of a registered application, service, website etc. A demonstration example has also been included highlighting the user log in experience when signing into an application that has integrated **AUTHENIX** as part of the user authentication process.

01

REGISTER AN APPLICATION, SERVICE OR WEBSITE:

Go to **AUTHENIX**: <https://www.authenix.eu/>, and fill in the required information in the application form. Registration must be done by the legal entity with responsibilities for the application which can be an organisation or an individual.

* indicates required input.

Operator Name ? *

Operator Homepage URL ?

Operator Postal Address ? *

Operator Contact Name ? *

Operator Contact Email ? *

Operator Country ? *

02

PROVIDE DETAILS ABOUT THE TYPE OF APPLICATION, SERVICE OR WEBSITE:

AUTHENIX's authorisation server supports different application types. Select the appropriate option of the authorisation code grant which is the application exchanges for an access token. Options include:

- **Client-side Web-Application** runs inside the Web-Browser (must use the OAuth2 Implicit Grant)
- **Server-side Web-Application** runs on a Web Server (must use the OAuth2 Authorisation Code Grant)

- **Mobile application** must use the Authorisation Code Grant and a redirect URI with application specific scheme, not http: or https
- **A Desktop application** must use the Authorisation Code Grant with a redirect URI specific for the application.
- **A Service application** must use the Client Credentials Grant and therefore has no redirect URI.

03

PROVIDE FURTHER INFORMATION ABOUT THE APPLICATION:

General information i.e. software version, application name, URL etc. is required as part of the process of releasing access tokens and can also include uploading the Terms of Use or Privacy Statement of the application:

The screenshot shows a form titled "General information" with the following fields and controls:

- Software Version**: A text input field with a question mark icon and an asterisk indicating it is required.
- Application Name**: A text input field with a question mark icon and an asterisk indicating it is required.
- Application Logo Upload**: A section with a "select file" button and a question mark icon.
- Application Logo URL**: A text input field with a question mark icon.
- Application Terms of Use URL**: A text input field with a question mark icon and an asterisk indicating it is required.

04

PERSONAL DATA POLICY SETTINGS:

As part of the registration process for each application etc., categories have to be selected indicating the type of information users will be required to provide (i.e. choose none, one or multiple options, or all):

- **IdP Policy**: indicates the use of a third-party platform to log in (Facebook, Google, University, etc.) and does not include the submission of personal information.
- **ID Policy**: creates a unique identifier for users but this does not require GDPR compliance, as no personal information is requested. A generated ID, it is not stored therefore cannot be used to identify the user.

- Profile Policy: requires the collection of personal information from users (name, surname, etc.)
- Email Policy: requires collecting of the user's email address

Please note: The default setting (i.e. *no policy option selected*) means that the user of the application would successfully login but after doing so acts anonymously. If the *Profile* or *Email* policies are selected, a privacy statement must be provided, informing users of the personal information to be collected, why and what their data will be used for.

05

CREATIVE COMMONS AND TERMS OF USE AGREEMENT:

A url link to a creative commons license as well as agreement to the [Terms of Use](#) of AUTHENIX are required to complete the registration process:

The screenshot shows a registration form titled "License information". It contains a text input field for "Creative Commons License URL" with a question mark icon to its right. Below the input field is a checkbox with the text: "I agree to the [The Terms of Use](#) of this service and confirm that operating this application does not violate any provisions set forth in the [Privacy Statement](#) of this service." At the bottom of the form is a green "Register" button.

06

CLICK REGISTER:

Once all the required fields are completed select the 'Register' button. Once registered Operators and registered applications are logged here: <https://www.authenix.eu/Operators>.

07

USE THE AUTHENIX AUTHENTICATION SERVICE:

Inform your user community about the use of AUTHENIX as an authentication service provider for your application etc. See example of the user experience signing in via AUTHENIX demonstrated by the integration and use of AUTHENIX to facilitate logging into the Cos4Cloud service: Cos4Bio: <https://cos4bio.eu/>.

Cos4Bio: Go to the [Cos4Bio platform](#) and click the sign in button:

A short description of **AUTHENIX** has been added and this appears in a pop up window as part of the Cos4Bio log in process:

To log in via **AUTHENIX**: users are redirected to the authentication service options:

Users can then log in using a selected provider option.

INFORMATION AND FURTHER SUPPORT

Introduction to this Cos4Cloud service: AUTHENIX: <https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/authenix-gdpr/>

Authenix website: <https://www.authenix.eu>

Registration page: <https://www.authenix.eu/registerapps>

Operators and registered applications: <https://www.authenix.eu/Operators>

Authenix API (OpenID Connect / OAuth2): <https://www.authenix.eu/API>

Access this service from the EOSC Marketplace: AUTHENIX: <https://marketplace.eosc-portal.eu/services/authenix>

Get the Cos4Cloud infographic for this service: [AUTHENIX Infographic](#)

Additional resources: [About the Cos4Cloud Toolbox and Evidence Hub](#)

This system and user guide is a training resource for AUTHENIX, one of the technological services co-designed by the Cos4Cloud project (<https://cos4cloud-eosc.eu/>). **Title: AUTHENIX System and User Guide.** Service Coordinator: Secure Dimensions. This guide is one of the Training and Capacity Building resources in the Cos4Cloud Toolbox & Evidence Hub developed by the Open University in collaboration with project partners. Contact: cos4cloud-toolbox@open.ac.uk.

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